

**IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS
OF ECOLOGICAL-VALEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE
FORMATION TECHNIQUES AMONG STUDENTS-PARENTS**

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**ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ ТА АНАЛІЗ ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ МЕТОДИКИ
ФОРМУВАННЯ ЕКОЛОГО-ВАЛЕОЛОГІЧНОЇ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ СТУДЕНТІВ-БАТЬКІВ**

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The article is dedicated to the problem of the ecological-valeological competence formation among the youth students. A brief description of the techniques of students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation is proposed.

Preparatory, main and final stages of the techniques of the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation realization have been characterized. The topic of the special course “Ecological-valeological” upbringing in the family” has been introduced. A didactic component of the techniques of students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation at every stage of its realization has been characterized.

A comparative analysis of the formation levels of students-parents' ecological-valeological competence of the control group and experimental groups at the stages of initial and final control in accordance with content, technological, evaluation-motivational and emotional-willingness criteria has been conducted. On its basis there has been made a result about the efficiency of the designed and HEE curriculum implemented process of students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation.

Key words: ecological-valeological competence, technique, formation, students-parents, criteria, efficiency, experiment.

The research topicality. The ecological-valeological competence formation of parents is about to become of the most current importance in the conditions of the modern development of Ukrainian society. This is subjected by the crying need of the environment preservation and enhancement and the need of educating psychologically, socially, and physically the young generation, which is going to be able to facilitate the development and prosperity of our state. It is evident, that the appropriate ecological-valeological upbringing must be exercised from the earliest age in the family circle when it requires the formed ecological-valeological competence from the parents. Along time with this, the number of scientific research is the evidence of insufficient design of the stated topic at the theoretical, methodical and practical levels.

The main publications analysis. Fundamental source of background for the research were scientific research and development works by domestic scientists Ju. Bojchuk [1], M. Goncharenko [2], V. Gorashhuk [3], M. Gryn'ova [4], V. Suhomlynsky [5], K. Yuryeva [6] and others.

The aim of the article lies in justifying the technique of students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation and its efficiency analysis.

The main material layout. The students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation was performed in the process of realization of the relevant technique developed by us. The choice of the target group was conditioned firstly by the fact that parents play the key role in the process of ecological-valeological education and upbringing of children in the family. In our opinion, the most favourable conditions for experimental research of the ecological-valeological competence formation process among the youth exist within the grounds of higher educational establishments. Consequently, young parents who do the correspondence studies in HEE took personal participation in our research.

In this case which specialty the students studied was not principle for us as in any case the ecological-valeological competence formation among students-parents while studying at a higher educational establishment is not devoted sufficient attention. The control group was formed from the students-parents with the total number of 224 respondents. Thus, the general selective totality of the experiment participants was 440 people.

The realization of the technique, which we introduced, foresaw a stage-by-stage implementation of various elements of its processual and content

components. At the same time at each stage of its realization — preparatory, main, concluding — the content of students-parents' teaching as well as organizational forms, techniques and ways of work with them changed in accordance with the task for each stage.

At the first (preparatory) stage the realization of the technique foresaw comprehension of the first part of the special course “Ecological-Valeological Upbringing in the Family” (topics: “Basic Ideas of the Course”, “Essentials of Children Upbringing in the Family”, “Theoretical Foundations of Valeological Upbringing of Children in the Family” by students. The didactic provision of the process of the ecological-valeological competence formation of young parents was designed mainly on active forms and teaching methods: lecture-discussion, problematic lecture-discussion, lecture-brainstorm, round table, the problem tasks method, ecological-psychological training, case-method and others.

At the second (main) stage of the realization the content component of the technique was provided by studying topics which composed the second part of the special course: “Methods of Ecological Education in the Family”, “Methods of Valeological Education in the Family”, “Organization of the Ecological-Valeological Activity of the Family”. The realization of the processual (didactic) component of the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation was provided at the expense of active and interactive (non-imitative and imitative) educational methods: lectures with the analysis of a certain situation, lecture-provocation, business game, technological practice, modeling and specific situation role playing method, project method and others.

The third (concluding) stage of realization of the proposed technique foresaw introduction of students with the third concluding part of the special course “Ecological-Valeological Upbringing in the Family” — “The Provision of the Research Activity on the Problem of Ecological-Valeological Education of Children in the Family”. The solving of the third stage tasks was provided by involving students-parents into the active scientific research work as for the problem of ecological-valeological education of children in the family. It occurred mainly in the process of performing creative-research tasks and their discussion in the form of express-conferences.

The important role at each of the stages of introducing the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation technique was devoted to the independent class and out-of-class work on each topic of the special course. In the process of the independent work students, applying creative thinking, solved a complex of relevant creative tasks.

The check of ecological-valeological competence formation technique efficiency was performed on the stage of the concluding control. After finishing the formational stage of the experiment it was stated that according to the *content criterion* in the control group on the moment of the concluding control (in comparison with initial control, which was performed at the stating stage of the experiment) the increase of the number of respondents, who reported a high level of ecological-valeological competence formation was by 4.1%. In the experimental group there have occurred much noticeable positive changes. In particular, the quantity of students with a high level of the component part formation of the ecological-valeological competence increased by 14.2% (which is 10.1% higher than the increase in the control group). The quantity of students-parents who have revealed a low level of the component part formation of the ecological-valeological competence in the control group decreased by 13.6%. In the experimental group such decrease was reduced by 56.2% that greatly increases the factors of the control group. The change dynamics of the content component part of the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation levels can be observed on the graph (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The dynamics of the content component part formation of the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence

The quantity of students-parents who have gained a high level of technological component formation of ecological-valeological competence in the control group made 4,9%, in the experimental one, their quantity at the end of the experiment formation stage made 18.2%. The quantity of students from

Figure 3. Dynamics of the value-motivational component part of ecological-valeological competence formation of students-parents

Almost similar the changes in the achieved results are also reported in accordance with emotional-volitional component part of the researched competence. In the experimental group the quantity of students who achieved a high level of this component formation has increased by 19.4% which is by 15.1% more than the increase in the control group. The quantity of students with a low level of emotional-volitional component part formation in the experimental group decreased by 35.7% in comparison with the control group. The dynamics of the emotional-volitional component part of the students-parents' ecological-valeological competence formation is given in the form of a graph (see Figure 4).

Conclusion. The diagnostics analysis of the ecological-valeological competence formation of students-parents performed at the concluding control stage allowed to determine a positive change dynamics among the experimental group students and reported considerable advantages of the high level of ecological-valeological competence formation in comparison with analogical figures of the control group students. This, consequently, has allowed making conclusions about the efficiency of the introduced technique.

Figure 4. **Dynamics of the emotional-volitional component part of ecological-valeological competence formation of students-parents**

The further research prospects lie in the realization of the developed technique in the system of postgraduate education, improvement of its content and didactic component parts, as well as the search for the possibilities of ecological-valeological competence formation of a wider range of parents.

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Єлізарова С. В. Впровадження та аналіз ефективності методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків

Стаття присвячена проблемі формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентської молоді. Пропонується стислий опис методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків.

Схарактеризовано підготовчий, основний та заключний етапи реалізації методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків. Наведено тематику спецкурсу «Еколого-валеологічне виховання в родині». Схарактеризовано дидактичну складову методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків на кожному етапі її реалізації.

Здійснено порівняльний аналіз рівнів сформованості еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків контрольної та експериментальної груп на етапах вихідного та підсумкового контролю за змістовним, технологічним, ціннісно-мотиваційним та емоційно-вольовим критеріями. На цій основі зроблено висновок про ефективність розробленої та впровадженої у навчальний процес ВНЗ методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-батьків.

Ключові слова: еколого-валеологічна компетентність, методика, формування, студенти-батьки, критерії, ефективність, експеримент.

Елизарова С. В. Внедрение и анализ эффективности методики формирования эколого-валеологической компетентности студентов-родителей

Статья посвящена проблеме формирования эколого-валеологической компетентности студенческой молодёжи. Предлагается короткое описание методики формирования эколого-валеологической компетентности студентов-родителей.

Охарактеризованы подготовительный, основной и заключительный этапы реализации методики формирования эколого-валеологической компетентности студентов-родителей. Приведена тематика спецкурса «Эколого-валеологическое воспитание в семье». Охарактеризован дидактический компонент методики формирования эколого-валеологической компетентности студентов-родителей на каждом этапе её реализации.

Осуществлён сравнительный анализ уровней сформированности эколого-валеологической компетентности студентов-родителей контрольной и экспериментальной групп на этапах исходного и итогового контроля по содержательному, технологическому, ценностно-мотивационному и эмоционально-волевому критериям. На этой основе сделан вывод об

ефективности розробленої та введеної в навчальний процес вузів методики формування еколого-валеологічної компетентності студентів-родителів.

Ключевые слова: еколого-валеологічна компетентність, методика, формування, студенти-родители, критерии, ефективність, експеримент.

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